

Enabling FAIR data in Geochemistry through the WorldFAIR Project

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Increasingly policy makers, funders, and publishers require geochemical datasets to be compliant with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) Principles^[1]. However, inconsistent interpretations of FAIR in geochemistry mean many researchers do not know what FAIR compliance entails and seek guidance. The [OneGeochemistry](#) initiative aims to establish global best practices for FAIR geochemical laboratory data.

OneGeochemistry participated in the CODATA and RDA-led [WorldFAIR Project on Global Cooperation on FAIR Data Policy and Practice](#), that was funded by the European Commission for 2022-2024 and collectively sought to advance implementation of the FAIR principles and improve Interoperability and Reusability by connecting initiatives on data management and FAIR data practices, including using [FAIR Implementation Profiles \(FIPs\)](#).

WorldFAIR developed guidelines to enhance uptake of FAIR both within and across disciplines, of which geochemistry was one of 11 disciplinary case studies (Chemistry, Nanomaterials, Geochemistry, Social Surveys, Population Health, Urban Health, Biodiversity, Agricultural Biodiversity, Oceans, Disaster Risk Reduction and Cultural Heritage). The Geochemistry case study enabled connections of geochemical groups building comprehensive and open access repositories, databases and/or networks to store, curate and make data and related objects FAIR, including physical samples, instruments, images, tools, etc.). The participating groups were [AuScope](#) (Australia); [EarthChem](#) and [Astromaterials Data System](#) (US); [EPOS Multi-scale Laboratories](#) (Europe); and [DIGIS Geochemical data for Georoc 2.0](#), [NFDI4Earth](#), and [GFZ Data Services](#) (Germany).

WorldFAIR and OneGeochemistry recommendations to increase FAIRness of geochemical data:

A dual approach to accelerating standards/best practices to enable FAIR compliance is recommended:

1. As geochemistry consists of multiple sub-disciplines, each with its own methods and terminologies, multiple working groups will be needed to develop required best practices for each; and
2. As there are already many community protocols and best practices at either the local, national or international level, there is an urgency to publish online current existing protocols, vocabularies, etc., with a view to forming focused international communities of practice to coalesce on global data agreements.

For greater detail, here is the list of WorldFAIR Geochemistry Case Study Outputs and Reports:

1) D5.1 Formalisation of OneGeochemistry

OneGeochemistry was formalised as a [CODATA Working Group](#) to give credibility and authority to pursue a long-term governance structure and enable OneGeochemistry to develop and promote influential, global, community-driven data conventions and best practices necessary to build a global network of high-quality, trusted geochemical data. OneGeochemistry has the endorsement of six Geochemical Societies [Read more](#).

2) Geochemistry Scientific Content Component (Milestone 6)

This Milestone describes progress towards developing a methodology designed to assist defining individual FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs) required to fully document each of the minimum scientific and technical variables used to describe any geochemical analysis. It was concluded that it was not possible to have a single FIP for all geochemical data. Rather, multiple FIPs will be required for each geochemistry and cosmochemistry subdiscipline and at different levels of granularity (dataset, database, discipline, repository). [Read more](#).

3) WorldFAIR Geochemistry Methodology and Outreach (D5.2)

This report advocates the utility of FIPs for the geochemistry community to foster alignment across the complex and heterogeneous geochemical data landscape. The report presents various ways in which the community can increase FAIRness of datasets through the publication of individual FIPs for different levels of both data granularity and community size (local, regional, international, global). [Read more](#)

4) WorldFAIR Guidelines for implementing Geochemistry Fair Implementation Profiles (FIPs) (D5.3)

This report and the associated reference FAIR Implementation Profile can be used by the geochemistry community – particularly by data creators and providers – to improve the FAIRness of their geochemical and cosmochemical datasets. [Read more](#).

^[1] Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I., Appleton, G., *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* **3**, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>